

The Effect of Employee Placement and Work Environment Through Work Spirit on ASN Performance at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang District

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Abstract: The current economic development requires every organization and agency to carry out good management in all aspects, including aspects of human resources. Human resources have an important role in determining the success or failure of an agency in achieving its goals, it is necessary to place the right employee. In carrying out the duties of a Bappededa employee, he must have the morals, knowledge, skills, and high morale that are needed in his position so that employees can carry out their duties professionally, effectively and efficiently. A good and comfortable work environment can also affect the level of employee morale and achieve high performance. The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of employee placement, work environment through morale on the performance of ASN BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency. The population of this study were all ASN employees at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency, totaling 60 people using the census method or saturated sample. Data analysis used descriptive statistical analysis and path analysis using SmartPLS software. The results showed that the placement of employees has a positive and significant effect on work morale, the work environment has a positive and significant effect on morale, the placement of employees has a positive and significant effect on performance, the work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance, and work morale has a positive and significant effect on performance. , Employee Placement and Work Environment indirectly affect the performance of ASN through Work Spirit.

Keywords: Employee placement, work environment, work spirit, ASN performance.

I. Introduction

The current economic development requires every organization and agency to carry out proper management in all aspects, including aspects of human resources. Human resources have an important role in determining the success or failure of an agency in achieving its goals. Human resources who are in the agency are usually called employees.

Employees are an important resource for the organization because they have the talent, energy and creativity that are needed by the organization to achieve its goals. The measure of success in achieving individual, team or organizational performance lies in the output produced. According to Mangkunegara (2013) performance is the result of an employee's work in terms of the quality and quantity of work achieved in carrying out tasks in accordance with the responsibilities given. Achievement of employee performance is needed both for employees from government and private agencies. According to Simanjuntak (2015) performance is the level of achievement of results on the implementation of certain tasks in this case including individual performance, group performance, performance influenced by internal and external factors.

The Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of Aceh Tamiang Regency is one of the government agencies that also demands the achievement of employee performance and organizational performance which is also the goal of the agency. BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency has the main task of assisting the Regent in carrying out the Aceh Tamiang Regency Government in the field of planning, and controlling development in accordance with statutory regulations, to support the smooth running of the main tasks of the Aceh Tamiang Regency Government in development, and to act as a regional technical institution that is responsible for development planning as mandated in article 14, paragraph (1), Law Number 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government, that one of the mandatory affairs under the authority of the regional government is development planning and control.

The organizational structure of the Regional Development Planning Agency, Aceh Tamiang Regency consists of: 1. Head of the Agency, 2. Secretariat, 3. Planning, Control and Evaluation, 4. Governance and Human Development, 5. Economy and Natural Resources, 6. Infrastructure and Regional Affairs, 7. Research and Development Sector, 8. Agency Technical Implementation Units and 9. Functional Position Groups.

The main tasks and functions of the Regional Development Planning Agency (BAPPEDA) of Aceh Tamiang Regency are based on the Regulation of the Aceh Tamiang Regent Number 68 of 2016 in article 5, that the Regional Development Planning Agency is in charge of carrying out government support and development affairs in the planning, research and development fields, hereinafter in article 6 that in order to carry out the tasks as referred to in article 5, the Regional Development Planning Agency has the following functions:

- a. Preparation of programs, guidelines and technical guidelines in the fields of planning, research and development;
- b. Formulation of technical policies in the field of regional planning and development as well as research and development;
- c. Coordinating development planning in the fields of government and human development, economy and natural resources as well as infrastructure and territory;
- d. Implementation of research and development of data collection, control, monitoring, evaluation and reporting on the implementation of regional development sourced from the district revenue and expenditure budget (APBK);
- e. Coordinating the preparation of budget plans sourced from the Aceh Revenue and Expenditure Budget (APBA), the State Budget (APBN), aids, loans and/or foreign grants;
- f. Implementation of data and information management of regional development as well as research and development;
- g. Preparation of materials for coordination meetings, evaluation and control of development planning as well as research and development;
- h. Implementation of coordination with other parties in the field of regional development planning as well as research and development;
- i. Fostering the agency's technical implementing unit and functional group of positions in accordance with the scope of their duties; and
- j. The implementation of other official duties assigned by the Regent in accordance with the field of duties and functions.

In addition to the tasks and functions of Bappeda described above, Bappeda also organizes Musrenbang at the district level and national level, prepares Regional Long-Term Development Plans, Regional Medium-Term Development Plans and Regional Annual Development Plans. Bappeda also controls and evaluates regional development by referring to the Minister of Home Affairs Regulation Number 86 of 2017 concerning Procedures for Planning, Controlling and Evaluation of Regional Development, Procedures for Evaluation of Draft Regional Regulations concerning Regional Long-Term Development Plans and Regional Medium-Term Development Plans and Plans, and Procedures for Amending Regional Long Term Development Plans, Regional Medium Term Development Plans and Regional Government Work Plans. Therefore, it is very influential on the agency's objectives, namely to improve services to the community, especially in the development planning process in order to achieve an expected target. The performance of BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang District employees is very important because employee performance will determine the success of an organization as is the case with Aceh Tamiang District BAPPEDA.

In carrying out his/her duties, a Bappeda employee must have the morale, knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed in his/her position so that employees can carry out their duties professionally, effectively, and efficiently. Things that need to be considered in the placement of employees are the suitability of their skills and expertise, in other words, the placement of employees must pay attention to the principle of the right man on the right place, Siswanto (2016). Employee placement is a process of assigning tasks and jobs to employees who have passed the selection process in accordance with the established scope (Intan, 2016). Placement of employees according to their skills and abilities will make it easier for employees to adapt and do their jobs so that they can produce good performance. The ability of employees who have been placed in appropriate job positions from the type of work applied for, a comfortable work environment and high morale are major assets in advancing the agency.

The placement of BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency employees in echelon positions is carried out through the inauguration of echelon officials, while for Implementers (staff) and Employees with Work Agreements (PDPK) are carried out by the Head of the General and Personnel Sub-Section with the knowledge of the Head of Bappeda. However, the placement of officials and implementers has not shown ideal conditions and is not fully in accordance with the results of the Position Analysis at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency. The results of the Position Analysis are used as a reference in the framework of formulating policies for fostering and structuring institutions, staffing, planning for education and training needs and evaluating policies for fostering and structuring institutions, staffing, planning for education and training needs. Based on observations made at Bappeda, there are problems with placement, such as

placing employees who are not in accordance with the educational background of Bappeda employees with areas of duty.

Based on initial observations, data found that the process of employee placement is still less than optimal where the fields and sub-fields that are filled in are not in accordance with what is needed. This indicates a description of the employee's incompatibility in working in accordance with the job specifications with the position of the position. So employees at work do not devote all their abilities which in the end result in decreased employee performance. However, there are also staff placements in appropriate sub-sectors and fields, such as the Secretariat, Program and Reporting sub-division, planning and funding sub-sector, Governance and Human Development, infrastructure and regional affairs, and Research and development.

In accordance with research conducted by Muljanto (2015) revealed that the mismatch of employee placement will be mismanaged or employee performance will not be optimal, where basic competencies that should be optimally utilized for organizational development, eventually freeze and are not utilized, as a result of placement mismatch. The same opinion was also expressed by Siswanto (2020), that the incompatibility of employee placement with competence and work environment can have an impact on the performance of an agency. Therefore, agencies need to improve the placement of employees in agencies so that employee performance can be achieved and increased.

The work environment is a series of factors that affect the performance of employees, both from individuals between individuals and facilities available at the agency (Pratama and Dian, 2018). Employee performance can also be influenced by the work environment according to Faris Afif (2020). The work environment is everything that is around employees that can affect employee behavior in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. According to Rahmawanti et. al. (2014) that the work environment is everything around employees both physically and non-physically that can affect them in carrying out all the work assigned to them.

The physical work environment that is often problematic at Bappeda Aceh Tamiang Regency is 1. the layout of the workplace is not in accordance with the room conditions 2. the lighting is still lacking, 3. the room temperature is not cold enough, 4. the work equipment is inadequate such as: Laptop , printer machines, infocus, filing cabinets, air conditioners and folio paper size photocopiers. 5. room for storage of documents or office archives which results in the accumulation of documents so that the room is not tidy, this affects the layout of the office layout so that documents are not organized and stored properly. Due to the uncomfortable work space so that it can affect the performance of employees, this is not in accordance with the wishes of the employee, causing discomfort at work, while the non-physical work environment includes cooperative relations between fields which is still low, so it can affect the performance of the agency.

The following are research results that prove that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance. According to Mangkunegara (2014) performance factors consist of internal factors and external factors, where internal factors are factors associated with employee characteristics, while external factors are factors that affect employee performance originating from the environment. In accordance with the results of research by Anggreni, et al (2018), the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The same result was also obtained by Syafitri (2020), that the work environment has an influence on performance. However, there are differences of opinion from the research results of Suhardi and Syaifullah (2017), that the work environment has a negative and significant effect on employee performance. According to Syalimono Siahaan, Syaiful Bahri (2019) Partially, the work environment variable has no significant effect on employee performance.

Morale is doing work more actively so that it is faster and better as expected (NitiseMITO, 2001). Employee morale can be measured from the willingness to work together, obedience to the provisions of the implementation of the work, and timeliness in completing the work. According to Busro (2018: 325), morale is a condition when working in an organization that shows strong feelings to carry out work and encourages employees to work better and more productively. The level of employee morale does not only depend on the employee himself, but also the extent to which the organization has the will to fulfill all the needs of its employees, both material and non-material needs, especially the needs related to the work of each employee.

Therefore, the management of an organization must be able to manage it properly so that employee morale can be maintained and improved so that performance can be achieved according to the target and even exceeds the target. In accordance with the results of Rahmat's research (2019), morale has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. However, different results were obtained by Anggreni, et al (2018), that work morale has a negative and significant effect on employee performance.

Based on field observations that Bappeda Aceh Tamiang employees still show a work spirit that is not optimal, it can be seen from the results of their employee performance, where employees often feel not optimistic and cheerful in carrying out their duties, this is illustrated by the employee's work attitude. The work carried out by employees often coincides with their own field work with other fields, such as: work on the preparation of the Regional Government Work Plan

(RKPD), Evaluation Control, often involves other fields in completing their work, while the Division also has main field tasks that must be completed.

According to Lestari, et.al.(2020) that in a research work spirit was stated in the form of a strong determination and visualized in a good work attitude (optimistic, cheerful, and enthusiastic). In addition, work spirit can be understood as sincerity, namely a disciplined and hardworking attitude in achieving organizational goals (Khamri & Heryanto, 2019). According to Sriasih et al. (2019), realistically the work spirit is in the form of diligent, careful, and hardworking behavior, thereby creating effectiveness in carrying out tasks.

Based on the results of the description above, it can be seen that the influence of employee placement and the work environment in Bappeda Aceh Tamiang Regency greatly affects employee morale, but not all employees experience a decrease in morale but there are several sub-sectors whose performance achievement is not optimal. The morale of employees at Bappeda can also be seen from the presence of BAPPEDA office employees in Aceh Tamiang Regency where employee absenteeism has increased. The increase in the percentage of employee absenteeism in 2020 was due to the covid-19 pandemic that employees did not come fully to work at the office but took turns working from home or Work From Home (WFH), so that employee performance was not optimal, based on the description above, it can be seen through the Recapitulation The attendance of BAPPEDA employees of Aceh Tamiang Regency is shown in the following table:

Table 1. Recapitulation of Employee Attendance at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency 2016-2020

Year	Keterangan				Number of Absent Employees	Percentage (%)
	Sick	Permission	Absent	Paid Leave		
2016	7	2	3	10	22	7.33
2017	6	5	0	6	17	5.67
2018	11	4	7	10	32	10.67
2019	19	6	8	4	37	12.33
2020	0	0	35	14	49	21.21

Table 1 shows that there are serious problems, employee absenteeism tends to increase every year, starting from 2016 to 2020, except in 2017 employee absenteeism has decreased compared to the previous year. This shows that the level of employee attendance affects performance.

Based on the observations, the researchers also found that in achieving performance there are still several programs whose performance targets are still low, and there are also program achievements that have exceeded predetermined performance targets such as the data and information development program and the Program for the Acceleration of the Implementation of Regional Planning Bureaucratic Reforms.

So from the placement of employees it affects the morale of employees, because employees have the knowledge and ability of the position or position they carry so that employees are not confused and awkward in doing work so that employees will be more enthusiastic about work, too much work and has a target completion time is too short so make employees feel bored with work. So it must be managed properly by the agency so that employee morale can increase, because morale has a fairly serious impact in optimizing the achievement of organizational goals. Likewise, a good work environment will make employees more enthusiastic about working because employees feel comfortable and safe while in the agency. This will support employees to achieve good performance as well.

II. Methodology

The type of research used is associative research with a quantitative approach. The definition of associative research method according to Sugiyono (2017) is research that aims to determine the effect or also the relationship between two or more variables.

While the quantitative approach according to Sugiyono (2017) can be interpreted as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or descriptive statistics with the aim of testing the established hypothesis.

The population in this study were all ASN employees at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency with a total population of 60 people. Sampling was carried out in accordance with the research objectives that had been determined. The sample is part of the population consisting of elements or objects that are expected to have the same characteristics as the population. The sampling technique used in this study using the census method or saturated sample, that is, all

populations are used or used as samples (Sugiyono, 2014). So that the total population in this study that was used as a sample was 60 people.

Data collection techniques used in this study are as follows:

- a. Questionnaire, (a list of questions) relating to Employee Placement, Work Environment, Work Spirit and ASN Performance. The questionnaire given is a closed questionnaire where respondents are only given the opportunity to choose the answers that have been provided according to their opinions, namely by providing a number of written statements that are used to obtain information from respondents.
- b. Interviews are conducting direct questions and answers to respondents, namely Bappeda employees of Aceh Tamiang Regency. Regarding the related information and information needed in this research.
- c. Observation is a data collection method that uses direct and indirect observations at the Bappeda of Aceh Tamiang Regency.
- d. Documents, namely by collecting and studying documents that exist in the Bappeda of Aceh Tamiang Regency, such as the number of employees, Regent's Regulations, Ranking List, Position Analysis Results at Bappeda Aceh Tamiang Regency in 2017 and others related to research.
- e. Journals related to the variables studied.
- f. Human Resource Management books, and those related to the variables studied.

This research uses data analysis method using SmartPLS software version 2.0.m3 which is run on computer media. According to Jogiyanto and Abdillah (2009) PLS (Partial Least Square) is: Variant-based structural equation analysis (SEM) which can simultaneously test the measurement model as well as test the structural model.

The measurement model is used to test the validity and reliability, while the structural model is used to test causality (testing hypotheses with predictive models). Furthermore, Jogiyanto and Abdillah (2009) stated that Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis is a multivariate statistical technique that makes comparisons between multiple dependent variables and multiple independent variables. PLS is a variant-based SEM statistical method designed to solve multiple regression when there are specific problems in the data.

Furthermore, Ghozali in Kalnadi (2013) explains that PLS is an analytical method that is soft modeling because it does not assume the data must be with a certain scale measurement, which means the number of samples can be small (under 100 samples). The fundamental difference between PLS, which is a variant-based SEM, and LISREL or AMOS, which is covariance-based, is the purpose of its use.

Structural model (inner model) is a structural model to predict causality between latent variables. Through the bootstrapping process, T-statistic test parameters were obtained to predict the existence of a causal relationship. The structural model (inner model) was evaluated by looking at the percentage of variance explained by the R2 value for the dependent variable using the Stone-Geisser Q-square test (Geisser, in Kalnadi 2013) and also looking at the magnitude of the structural path coefficient.

The formation of a path diagram in the SEM process is a visualization of the research conceptual framework so that it is easier to understand and learn. In addition, this path diagram will be tested through goodness of fit to see the suitability of the model with existing reality (Sugiyono, 2013).

The formation of the path diagram must pay attention to the construct of exogenous or endogenous variables with the manifest variables of each of these latent variables. The submission of a research structural model based on the conceptual framework under study is as follows:

Figure 1. Research Flowchart Model

In the flow chart, the magnitude of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables is symbolized by gamma (γ) and the effect of endogenous variables is symbolized by beta (β). The level of influence of factors outside the research model (error).

The equation obtained from the flow chart conversion consists of:

- a. The measurement model specification equation (Measurement Model) or the outer model, namely the specification of the relationship between latent variables and their indicators, also known as outer relations, defines the characteristics of the construct and its manifest variables.
- b. Structural equation (Structural Equation) or inner model, which is formulated to express the causality relationship between various constructs.

The parameter estimation method (estimation) in PLS is the least square method. The calculation process is carried out by iteration, where the iteration will stop if a convergent condition has been reached. Parameter estimation in PLS includes 3 things, namely:

- a. Weight estimate is used to create a latent variable score
- b. The path estimate that connects the latent variables and the loading estimate between the latent variables and their indicators.
- c. Means and parameter locations (regression constant values, intercepts) for indicators and latent variables.

III. Results

Frequency of Respondents' Answers

The description of the respondent's answers describes how the distribution of respondents' answers to the questions asked in the questionnaire. The following shows the distribution of respondents' answers regarding the Work Placement variable (X1), Work Environment variable (X2), Work Spirit variable (Z) and ASN Performance (Y). The frequency of respondents can be seen in the following table:

- a. Distribution of Respondents' Answers to the Work Placement Variable (X1)

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents' Answers to the Work Placement Variable (X1)

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Not Agree		Quite Agree		Agree		Very Agree		Mean	Description
	f	%	F	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
I was placed in the current position according to the results of my academic grades	1	1.67	6	10	24	40	17	28.33	12	20	3.55	In accordance
Strategic employee positions are filled by employees who have good achievements	7	11.67	6	10	25	41.67	13	21.67	9	15	3.18	Not Suitable
The position occupied by the employee is in accordance with the educational background of the employee	2	3.33	1	1.67	22	36.67	26	43.33	9	15	3.65	In accordance
I was placed in a position or position that I have occupied before	4	6.67	1	1.67	15	25	27	45	13	21.67	3.73	In accordance
Employees are placed in positions or positions that are in accordance with the training the employee has attended	4	6.67	3	5	26	43.33	20	33.33	7	11.67	3.38	Not Suitable
The placement of each employee is always in accordance with the employee's area of expertise	1	1.67	1	1.67	15	25	23	38.33	20	33.33	4	In accordance
Average Respondents' Answers for Job Placement											3,53	In accordance

Table 2 proves that the job placement is appropriate based on the answers of respondents who are Bappeda employees in Aceh Tamiang District. The appropriate placement of employees is proven from the answers of the highest respondents as many as 20 respondents with a mean value of (4) is with the statement Placement of each employee is always in accordance with his field of expertise, namely at the Bappeda Secretariat of Aceh Tamiang Regency, Planning and Funding Sub-Sector, Data and Sub-Sector Reporting and Administration and Human Development. As for the Respondents' answers that are not appropriate in the statement of strategic employee positions, filled by employees who have good achievements, this shows that in placing employees at Bappeda they do not really look at the achievements of employees and statements that employees are placed in positions or positions that are in accordance with the training they have attended. employees, this shows that the training followed by the employee after the employee occupies the position, so that the training followed is in accordance with the position of the position and increases the employee's knowledge about their field of work.

Based on Table 2, it is known that the distribution of answers for the Work Placement variable was distributed to 60 respondents, namely:

1. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I was placed in the current position according to the results of my academic scores), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, 6 respondents who answered inappropriately (10%), respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 24 respondents (40%), respondents who answered appropriate as many as 17 respondents (28.33%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 12 respondents (20%). The mean value of question one is 3.55 which means it is appropriate.
2. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (strategic employee positions are filled by employees who have good performance), indicating that there are 7 (11.67%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, 6 respondents answered inappropriately (10%)), respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 25 respondents (41.67%), respondents who answered appropriate as many as 13 respondents (21.67%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 9 respondents (15%). The mean value of question two is 3.18 which means it is not appropriate.
3. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (the position occupied by the employee according to the educational background of the employee), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, the respondents who answered inappropriately were 1 respondent (1, 67%), respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 22 respondents (36.67%), respondents who answered correctly as many as 26 respondents (43.33%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 9 respondents (15%). The mean value of question three is 3.65 which means it is appropriate.
4. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I was placed in a position or position that I have occupied before), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, 1 respondent who answered inappropriately (1, 67%), respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 15 respondents (25%), respondents who answered appropriate as many as 27 respondents (45%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 13 respondents (21.67%). The mean value of question four is 3.73 which means it is appropriate.
5. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (Employees are placed in positions or positions that are in accordance with the training that employees have attended), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, respondents who answered inappropriately were 3 respondents (5 %), respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 26 respondents (43.33%), respondents who answered appropriate as many as 20 respondents (33.33%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 7 respondents (11.67%). The mean value of question five is 3.38 which means it is not appropriate.
6. Distribution of respondents' answers to questions (The placement of each employee is always in accordance with the employee's area of expertise), indicating that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered very inappropriately, 1 respondent who answered inappropriately (1.67%) , respondents who answered less appropriate as many as 15 respondents (25%), respondents who answered according to as many as 23 respondents (38.33%) and respondents who answered very well as many as 20 respondents (33.33%). The mean value of question six is 4 which means it is appropriate.

b. Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Work Environment Variables (X2)

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents' Answers to Work Environment Variables (X2)

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Not Agree		Quite Agree		Agree		Very Agree		Mean	Description
	F	%	f	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
The size of my workspace according to my work needs	1	1.67	1	1.67	13	21.67	25	41.67	20	33.33	4.03	Agree
The layout of my workspace is in accordance with my work needs	2	3.33	6	10	21	35	21	35	10	16.67	3.52	Agree
My work place is clean	1	1.67	4	6.67	21	35	21	35	13	21.67	3.68	Agree
My equipment at work is adequate to support my work	1	1.67	4	6.67	21	35	24	40	10	16.67	3.63	Agree
The air temperature in my room is very cold	3	5	3	5	23	38.33	22	36.67	9	15	3.52	Agree
WC or bathroom facilities are adequate with employee needs	2	3.33	2	3.33	9	15	32	53.33	15	25	3.93	Agree
Supervision of work is carried out routinely by the agency	2	3.33	6	10	29	48.33	17	28.33	6	10	3.32	Not Agree
I have a harmonious relationship with coworkers	2	3.33	2	3.33	8	13.33	24	40	24	40	4.1	Agree
I get rewarded according to the performance I give to the agency	1	1.67	4	6.67	14	23.33	24	40	17	28.33	3.87	Agree
I have a wise boss	4	6.67	4	6.67	23	38.33	14	23.33	15	25	3.53	Agree
Average respondents' answers for the work environment											3,7	Agree

Table 3 proves that the Work Environment in the Bappeda of Aceh Tamiang Regency has shown a good condition, this is evidenced by the respondents' answers, but the answers of respondents who stated they did not agree with the statement. Supervision of work is carried out routinely by the agency, the supervision carried out by Bappeda on the work of employees is not carried out regularly. routinely by the agency because there is work that is carried out every month so there is no need for routine supervision to be carried out.

Based on Table 3, it is known that the distribution of answers for the Work Environment variable was distributed to 60 respondents, namely:

1. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (The size of my workspace is in accordance with the needs of my work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 1 respondent (1.67%) , respondents who answered less agree as many as 13 respondents (21.67%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 25 respondents (41.67%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 20 respondents (33.33%). The mean value of question one is 4.03 which means agree.
2. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (The layout in my workspace is in accordance with the needs of my work), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 6 respondents (10%), respondents who answered less agree were 21 respondents (35%), respondents who answered agreed were 21 respondents (35%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 10 respondents (16.67%). The mean value of question two is 3.52 which means agree.

3. Distribution of respondents' answers to the question (My place of work is clean), indicating that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed were 4 respondents (6.67%), respondents who answered less agreed as many as 21 respondents (35%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 21 respondents (35%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed as many as 13 respondents (21.67%). The mean value of question three is 3.68 which means agree.
4. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (My equipment at work is adequate to support my work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 4 respondents who answered disagreed (6.67%), respondents who answered less agree were 21 respondents (35%), respondents who answered agreed were 24 respondents (40%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 10 respondents (16.67%). The mean value of question four is 3.63 which means agree.
5. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (The air temperature in my room is very cool), shows that there are 3 (5%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 3 respondents who answered disagreed (5%), respondents who answered disagreed as much as 23 respondents (38.33%), respondents who answered agreed were 22 respondents (36.67%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 9 respondents (15%). The mean value of question five is 3.52 which means agree.
6. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (WC or bathroom facilities are adequate with the needs of employees), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 2 respondents (3.33%), respondents who answered disagreed as many as 9 respondents (15%), respondents who answered agreed were 32 respondents (53.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 15 respondents (25%). The mean value of question six is 3.93 which means agree.
7. Distribution of respondents' answers to the question (Supervision of work is carried out routinely by the agency), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed were 6 respondents (10%), respondents who answered disagree as much as 29 respondents (48.33%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 17 respondents (28.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 6 respondents (10%). The mean value of question seven is 3.32, which means that you do not agree.
8. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I have a harmonious relationship with co-workers), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 2 respondents who answered disagreed (3.33%) respondents who answered disagreed as many as 8 respondents (13.33%), respondents who answered agreed were 24 respondents (40%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 24 respondents (40%). The mean value of question eight is 4.1 which means agree.
9. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I get a reward according to the performance that I give to the agency), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 4 respondents who answered disagree (6, 67%), respondents who answered disagreed as many as 14 respondents (23.33%), respondents who answered agreed were 24 respondents (40%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 17 respondents (28.33%). The mean value of question nine is 3.87 which means agree.
10. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I have a wise boss), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 4 respondents (6.67%), respondents who answered disagree as many as 23 respondents (38.33%), respondents who answered agree as many as 14 respondents (23.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 15 respondents (25%). The mean value of the ten questions is 3.53, which means agree.

c. Distribution Answers Respondents Toward Variable Work Spirit (Z)

Table 4. Distribution Answers Respondents Toward Variable Work Spirit (Z)

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Very Not Agree		Not Agree		Agree		Very Agree		Mean	Description
	F	%	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
I finish the job professionally	1	1.67	0	0	6	10	16	26.67	37	61.67	4.47	Very Agree
I don't procrastinate on the work assigned to me	2	3.33	1	1.67	18	30	22	36.67	17	28.33	3.85	Agree
I always try to get the job done quickly	1	1.67	4	6.67	20	33.33	21	35	14	23.33	3.72	Agree
I am always present during work time	1	1.67	4	6.67	18	30	19	31.67	18	30	3.82	Agree
I am always present at every activity outside the Job Description	4	6.67	6	10	22	36.67	19	31.67	9	15	3.38	Not Agree

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Very Not Agree		Not Agree		Agree		Very Agree		Mean	Description
	F	%	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
I am always loyal to the agency where I work	1	1.67	0	0	4	6.67	25	41.67	30	50	4.38	Very Agree
I am happy to work in the current agency	1	1.67	5	8.33	20	33.33	18	30	16	26.67	3.72	Agree
I always feel satisfied with my work	1	1.67	1	1.67	9	15	26	43.33	23	38.33	4.15	Agree
I feel calm in completing my work	1	1.67	0	0	5	8.33	20	33.33	34	56.67	4.43	Very Agree
Average respondent's answer for Work Spirit											4	Agree

Based on Table 4 proves that the Work Spirit of Bappeda employees in Aceh Tamiang Regency has high work morale in accordance with the respondents' answers distributed by researchers, as evidenced by the answers of respondents with the highest mean value (4.47) with my statement completing the work professionally, this shows that the employee Bappeda completes the assigned tasks in a professional manner, meaning that the right placement of employees will complete the job well. Respondent's answer Disagree with the statement I am always present at every activity outside the Job Description, this shows that Bappeda employees do not interfere too much which is not their duty and responsibility.

It is known that the distribution of answers in table 4 for the variable of Work Spirit which is distributed to 60 respondents, namely:

1. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I finished my work professionally), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 6 respondents who answered disagreed (10%), respondents who answered agreed as much as 16 respondents (26.67%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 37 respondents (61.67%). The mean value of question one is 4.47 which means strongly agree.
2. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I do not delay the work assigned to me), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 1 respondent who answered disagreed (1.67%) 18 respondents who answered disagree (30%), 22 respondents who answered agreed (36.67%) and 17 respondents who answered strongly agree (28.33%). The mean value of question two is 3.85 which means agree.
3. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I always try to finish work quickly), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 4 respondents (6.67%) who answered disagree as much as 20 respondents (33.33%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 21 respondents (35%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 14 respondents (23.33%). The mean value of question three is 3.72 which means agree.
4. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I am always present during work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 4 respondents (6.67%) 18 respondents answered disagree (30%), 19 respondents agreed (31.67%) and 18 respondents (30%). The mean value of question four is 3.82 which means agree.
5. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I am always present at every activity outside the Job Description), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 6 respondents (10%), respondents 22 respondents (36.67%) answered disagree, 19 respondents agreed (31.67%) and 9 respondents (15%). The mean value of question five is 3.38, which means that you do not agree.
6. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I have always been loyal to the agency where I work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered less agree were 4 respondents (6.67%) respondents who answered agreed as many as 25 respondents (41.64%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed as many as 30 respondents (50%). The mean value of question six is 4.38 which means strongly agree.
7. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I enjoy working in the current agency), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 5 respondents who answered disagreed (8.33%), respondents who answered disagree as much as 20 respondents (33.33%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 18 respondents (30%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 16 respondents (26.67%). The mean value of question seven is 3.72 which means agree.
8. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I always feel satisfied with my work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed were 1

respondent (1.67%), respondents who answered disagree as many as 9 respondents (15%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 26 respondents (43.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 23 respondents (38.33%). The mean value of the eight questions is 4.15 which means agree.

- The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I feel calm in completing my work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered less agree were 5 respondents (8.33%), respondents who answered agree as many as 20 respondents (33.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 34 respondents (56.67%). The mean value of question nine is 4.43 which means strongly agree.

d. Distribution of Respondents' Answers To Performance Variable (Y)

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents' Answers To Performance Variable (Y)

Statement	Strongly Disagree		Very Not Agree		Not Agree		Agree		Very Agree		Mean	Description
	f	%	F	%	f	%	F	%	f	%		
I am always meticulous at work.	1	1.67	0	0	6	10	27	45	26	43.33	4.28	Strongly Disagree
I have knowledge about my job.	6	10	7	11.67	22	36.67	12	20	13	21.67	3.32	Not Agree
I finish the job with good accuracy.	2	3.33	1	1.67	22	36.67	26	43.33	9	15	3.65	Agree
I can always use my work time efficiently.	4	6.67	1	1.67	15	25	27	45	13	21.67	3.73	Agree
I always finish work on time.	4	6.67	3	5	26	43.33	20	33.33	7	11.67	3.38	Agree
The work I complete is always on target.	1	1.67	1	1.67	15	25	23	38.33	20	33.33	4	Agree
I provide the best service to the community.	1	1.67	1	1.67	13	21.67	25	41.67	20	33.33	4.03	Agree
I always have integrity in every job done.	2	3.33	6	10	21	35	21	35	10	16.67	3.52	Agree
I am always committed to working well for the agency.	1	1.67	4	6.67	21	35	21	35	13	21.67	3.68	Agree
Average respondents' answers for Performance											3,73	Agree

Table 5 proves that the performance of Bappeda employees in Aceh Regency is good, this is evidenced by the results of the answers from respondents, which almost all statements with an average answer indicate a mean value (3.73). Respondents' answers Disagree with the statement I have knowledge about my job, based on observations made by researchers on the statement that employees in carrying out work are sometimes outside of the employee's main duties, where in the employee job description there is one employee job description, namely the implementation of other tasks given by superiors, so that not all tasks assigned by superiors employees know clearly about the job.

Based on Table 5, it is known that the distribution of answers for the Performance variable distributed to 60 respondents is:

- The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I am always careful at work), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed were 6 respondents (10%), respondents who answered agreed were as many as 27 respondents (45%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 26 respondents (43.33%).
- The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I have knowledge about my work), shows that there are 6 (10%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed were 7 respondents (11.67%), respondents who answered less agree as many as 22 respondents (36.67%), respondents who answered agree as many as 12 respondents (20%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 13 respondents (21.67%). The mean value of question two is 3.32, which means that you do not agree.

3. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I completed the work with good accuracy), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 1 respondent (1.67%), respondents who answered disagree as much as 22 respondents (36.67%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 26 respondents (43.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 9 respondents (15%). The mean value of question three is 3.65 which means agree.
4. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I can always use my work time efficiently), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 1 respondent who answered disagreed (1.67%) , respondents who answered less agree as many as 15 respondents (25%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 27 respondents (45%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 13 respondents (21.67%). The mean value of question four is 3.73 which means agree.
5. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I always finish my work on time), shows that there are 4 (6.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 3 respondents who answered disagreed (5%), respondents who answered less agree as many as 26 respondents (43.33%), respondents who answered agree as many as 20 respondents (33.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 7 respondents (11.67%). The mean value of question three is 3.38 which means agree.
6. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (The work I complete always matches the specified target), indicating that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 1 respondent who answered disagreed (1.67%) , respondents who answered less agree as many as 15 respondents (25%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 23 respondents (38.33%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 20 respondents (33.33%). The mean value of question three is 4 which means agree.
7. The distribution of respondents' answers to the question (I provide the best service to the community), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, respondents who answered disagreed as many as 1 respondent (1.67%), respondents who answered less agree as many as 13 respondents (21.67%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 25 respondents (41.67%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 20 respondents (33.33%). The mean value of question three is 4.03 which means agree.
8. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I always have integrity in every work done), shows that there are 2 (3.33%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 6 respondents who answered disagree (10%), respondents who answered disagree as much as 21 respondents (35%), respondents who answered agreed as many as 21 respondents (35%) and respondents who answered strongly agree as many as 10 respondents (16.67%). The mean value of question three is 3.52 which means agree.
9. The distribution of respondents' answers to questions (I am always committed to working well in the agency), shows that there are 1 (1.67%) respondents who answered strongly disagree, 4 respondents who answered disagreed (6.67%) , respondents who answered disagree were 21 respondents (35%), respondents who answered agreed were 21 respondents (35%) and respondents who answered strongly agreed were 13 respondents (21.67%). The mean value of question three is 3.68 which means agree.

The results of the SmartPLS algorithm in assessing the path coefficient directly are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Path Coefficients

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Employee Placement -> Work Spirit	0,216	0,227	0,114	3,887	0,030
Employee Placement -> ASN Performance	0,456	0,469	0,084	5,442	0,000
Work Environment -> Work Spirit	0,721	0,709	0,115	6,258	0,000
Employee Placement -> ASN Performance	0,403	0,397	0,094	4,283	0,000
Work Spirit -> ASN Performance	0,370	0,061	0,069	4,819	0,004

The following is a discussion of each hypothesis test based on the test results which are summarized in Table 6:

1. The Effect of Work Placement on Work Morale. Based on Table 4.13 explains that the effect of work placement on work morale ($p = 0.030 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected. H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between work placement and work spirit.
2. The Effect of Work Placement on Performance. Based on Table 4.13 explains that the effect of work placement on performance ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected. H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between work placement and performance.

3. The Influence of Work Environment on Work Morale. Based on Table 4.13 explains that the influence of the work environment on work morale ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected. H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between the work environment and work spirit.
4. Influence of Work Environment on Performance. Based on Table 4.13 explains that the influence of the Work Environment on Performance ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between the Work Environment and Performance.
5. The Influence of Work Morale on Performance. Based on Table 4.13 explains that the influence of work morale on performance ($p = 0.004 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected, H_1 is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between morale and performance.

Indirect influence is the amount of influence through the mediating variable. The magnitude of the indirect effect is the product of the direct effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable and the direct effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable, the magnitude of the indirect effect of the independent variable on the variable can be calculated and summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Indirect Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Environment-> Work Spirit -> ASN Performance	2,851	0,043	0,051	3,425	0,000
Employee Placement-> Work Spirit -> ASN Performance	1,815	0,014	0,019	4,811	0,000

Based on Table 4.14, the results of the study to answer the hypotheses contained in the previous chapter are as follows:

1. The Effect of Work Placement on Performance through Work Morale Table 7 shows that there is an indirect effect of Job Placement on Performance through Morale is 2.851, with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.005$, it can be concluded that Job Placement has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Enthusiasm Work.
2. The Effect of Work Environment on Performance through Work Morale Table 7 shows that there is an indirect effect of the Work Environment on Performance through Morale is 1.815, with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.005$, it can be concluded that the Work Environment has a positive and significant effect on Performance through Enthusiasm Work.

IV. Conclusion

Based on the analysis and discussion of the influence of motivation, organizational commitment, and leadership on nurse work stress in improving nurse performance at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan, several conclusions can be drawn, namely, motivation has a negative and significant effect on work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital, Medan. Organizational commitment has a negative but not significant effect on work stress. Leadership has a negative and significant effect on work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at Royal Prima Hospital, Medan. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

Based on the analysis and discussion on the Influence of Employee Placement and Work Environment through Work Spirit at the Regional Development Planning Agency of Aceh Tamiang Regency, several conclusions and suggestions can be drawn as follows:

1. Employee Placement has a positive and significant effect on Work Spirit at Bappeda Aceh Tamiang Regency.
2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on morale at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency.
3. Employee Placement has a positive and significant effect on ASN Performance at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency.
4. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of ASN at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency.
5. Morale has a positive and significant effect on the performance of ASN at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency.
6. Employee placement has an indirect effect on ASN Performance through Work Spirit at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency.

7. The work environment has an indirect effect on the performance of ASN through the spirit of work at BAPPEDA, Aceh Tamiang Regency.

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions above, the suggestions and inputs aimed at providing information for goodness and progress in improving the performance of ASN in the Regional Development Planning Agency of Aceh Tamiang Regency are as follows:

1. Work placement has a positive and significant effect on performance and also through work enthusiasm, this shows that job placement is very good, but there are still problems in work placement where work placements at BAPPEDA Aceh Tamiang Regency still have not provided job placements for employees who have good performance. good, employees who have achievements are assets for the agency, because their achievements can provide a good assessment for the agency and can also improve the performance of the agency, the placement of employees in Bappeda also needs to be considered. Educational background in accordance with the field of work, and also needs to pay attention to the principles the right man on the right place, so there is a match between education and the placement of tasks in Bappeda Aceh Tamiang Regency, so that employees can complete job descriptions that are burdened by employees, so that employee performance is also high. The agency also focuses on its human resources by looking at the achievements of employees. Employees who have good performance, of course, must be supported by being given more training in accordance with the work assigned at this time, so that they can become leaders for future agencies. Leaders in Bappeda must also pay attention to improving the skills possessed by employees. The expertise followed by the employee will certainly increase the ability and competence of the employee, so this must be developed by the agency so that every employee has the opportunity to develop his abilities. Agencies must also see and provide opportunities for training that is followed by employees and adjust it to work placements that are in accordance with the expertise being followed because with these skills, of course, employees will be able to apply them to the field of work assigned to them. Therefore, the agency must place employees, both in positions and implementing staff, in accordance with the training followed by employees.
2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on performance and also through morale, it is known that the employee's work environment is good and needs to be maintained by the agency, but there are some problems felt by the employee, where there is still no routine supervision carried out by the agency. So this makes employees less in coordination with between employees and superiors so that discommunication between fellow employees can be minimized. In this case the agency must routinely supervise the work of employees, and also the importance of providing socialization or holding meetings of all employees to see the performance of employees, this is done so that the agency can give appreciation to employees who have good achievements in their work environment, as well as with several room layouts by employees who still need to be considered where there is still a need for storage for documents. This is of course very much needed especially in work, the documents that will be stored will be very useful in the future.
3. Morale also has a positive and significant effect on performance, this shows that morale must be maintained and improved, it is known that employee morale is good, where employees are very professional and always complete work on time. However, there are still some employees who are sometimes absent when there are activities outside the job description, respondents think that these activities are not too important. In this case, the agency must be more persuasive in inviting employees to be involved in activities outside of the agency's job description because to increase employee knowledge outside of their duties, the leader or superior must provide socialization of the important benefits of the activities carried out and also provide compensation for employees who are active in participating in activities carried out. carried out by the agency so as to increase morale for employees.
4. The performance of Bappeda employees in Aceh Tamiang Regency is seen from the achievement of program targets. The program is already good. Work Placement, Work Environment and Work Morale on positive and significant performance. This shows that Bappeda's ASN performance in Aceh Tamiang District is already high and that almost all of the programs that are the tasks and responsibilities that must be completed by Bappeda are in accordance with the predetermined targets and time. Placement of employees is in accordance with their education and expertise where employees can complete work professionally. Employees who are placed in Bappeda are employees who are always loyal to the agency where the employee is assigned so that they can be maintained and guarded by the Bappeda agency. Suggestions Researchers to be able to pay attention to added value or compensation and motivation on employee performance to always be enthusiastic at work.
5. Due to the limitations of the researcher, it is hoped that future researchers will further refine this research by using factors other than those studied by the researcher, so that more complete information will be obtained about what factors affect performance, further researchers can add variables others such as adaptability, leadership and motivation or can research other agencies in order to obtain more findings.

References

- [1.] Achmad Kuncoro, Engkos dan Riduwan. 2011. *Cara Menggunakan dan Memaknai Path Analysis (Analisis Jalur)*. Alfabeta. Bandung.
- [2.] Ghozali, Imam. 2016. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate dengan Program SPSS*. Cetakan Keempat. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [3.] Gomes, Faustino dan Cardoso. 2010. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Pertama. Cetakan Kedua. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [4.] Elbadiansyah. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Pertama. Malang: IRDH.
- [5.] Handoko, T, Hani. 2012. *Manajemen Personalia dan Sumber Daya Manusia*. Edisi Kedua. Yogyakarta : BPFE UGM.
- [6.] Hasibuan, Melayu S.P. 2013. *Organisasi dan Motivasi*. Bumi Aksara. Jakarta.
- [7.] Hasibuan. 2013. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Ketujuh Belas. Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara.
- [8.] Mangkunegara, Anwar. Prabu. 2010. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- [9.] Moekijat. 2012. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. CV Mandar Maju. Bandung.
- [10.] Noor, Arifin. 2018. *Manajemen Sumberdaya Manusia Teori dan Kasus*. Cetakan Pertama. Jakarta: UNINSNU Press.
- [11.] Nurdin, Batjo, Mahadin. 2019. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Pertama. Makassar: Penerbit Aksara Timur.
- [12.] Rivai, Veithzal. 2015. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia untuk Perusahaan, dari Teori ke Praktek*. Edisi Pertama. Cetakan Ketiga. Jakarta: Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [13.] Sugiyono. 2016. *Metode Penelitian Bisnis*. Cetakan Keenambelas, Bandung:Penerbit Alfabeta.
- [14.] Sukmawati, Marjuni. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Pertama. Makassar: Sah Media.
- [15.] Sri, Larasati. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan Pertama. Yogyakarta: Budi Utama.
- [16.] Sunyoto. 2014. *Manajemen Sumber Data manusia*. Cetakan Pertama. Pongoro: Uwais Inspirasi Indonesia.yono.
- [17.] Sutrisno, Edi. 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Cetakan ke 8 . Jakarta. Prenadamedia Grup. Muljanto, M. A. (2015). Menumbuhkan Pola Pikir, Sikap, dan Perilaku Positif sebagai Pegawai Negeri Sipil. *Jurnal Hukum Republica*. 14(1), 45- 64.
- [18.] Siswanto, E. (2020). Persepsi Kesesuaian Penempatan Pegawai Dalam Menunjang Peningkatan Kinerja BBPK Ciloto Tahun 2020. *Jurnal Riset Teknologi dan Inovasi Pendidikan (JARTIKA)*, 3(2), 312-321
- [19.] Intan Masyichah, Dewi Prihatini, Muhammad Syaharudin. (2016). Pengaruh Penempatan Karyawan, Pengalaman Kerja Serta Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Loyalitas Karyawan dan Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. PLN (Persero) Area Banyuwangi. "<http://repository.unej.ac.id/>".
- [20.] Rondo, Rosalina dan Hendra. (2018). Pengaruh Kepribadian, Lingkungan Kerja dan Penempatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan (Pada PT. BPR Dana Manado). *Jurna EMBA Vol.6 No.4*, 2848-2857
- [21.] Suhardi dan Syaifullah.2017. Pengaruh Motivasi, Kompetensi, Lingkungan Kerja, Kompensasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior dan Kinerja Karyawan Asuransi Jiwa di Provinsi Kepulauan Riau. *Jurnal Benefita* 2 (1) Februari 2017 (55-71). Batam
- [22.] Rahmat, Yogie. 2019. THE EFFECT OF WORK SPIRIT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE IN KFC BRANCH OF SUDIRMAN PEKANBARU. *e-Jurnal Apresiasi Ekonomi Volume 7, Nomor 2, Mei 2019* : 159 -168. ISSN Cetak : 2337-3997 ISSN Online :2613-9774. Riau.
- [23.] Kaswan 2015.Sikap Kerja. Bandung : Alfabeta.

- [24.] Sunyoto, Danang. 2015. Manajemen dan Pengembangan Sumber Daya Manusia (Cetakan Pertama). Yogyakarta : CAPS (Center for Academic Publishing Service).
- [25.] Priansa, D.J. (2016) Perencanaan dan Pengembangan SDM. Bandung Alfabeta.
- [26.] Wahyuningsih, Sri. 2014. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Kecamatan Tering Kabupaten Kutai Barat. *Jurnal Pemerintahan Intergratif*, 2 (1), pp : 70-84.
- [27.] Muljanto, M. A. (2015). Menumbuhkan Pola Pikir, Sikap, dan Perilaku Positif sebagai Pegawai Negeri Sipil. *Jurnal Hukum Republica*. 14(1), 45- 64.
- [28.] Dharma Pasaribu, Panca. 2017. Pengaruh lingkungan kerja terhadap semangat kerja pegawai pada CV. Jaya Karya Pekanbaru. *JOM FISIP Vol. 4 No. 1 - Februari 2017*.
- [29.] Dwi Handayani, Rina. 2016. Pengaruh Lingkungan Dan Semangat Kerja Terhadap Kinerja PNS Balitsa Lembang. *Pariwisata*, Vol. II No.1 April 2016. ISSN: 2355-6587.
- [30.] Putri, Ni Made Dewi Kansa. 2018. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Dengan Semangat Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening Pada Dinas Kesehatan Kabupaten Tabanan Bali STMIK Royal - AMIK Royal, hlm. 667 - 672 ISSN 2622-6510 (online) *Kisaran, Asahan, Sumut - 3 September 2018*.
- [31.] Nasib dan Martin. 2018. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Dan Insentif Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. STMIK Royal - AMIK Royal, hlm. 423 - 428 ISSN 2622-6510 (online) *Kisaran, Asahan, Sumut - 3 September 2018*.
- [32.] Rikindaka Awaliwinda, Marlia Saridewi, Lia Suprihartini. 2018. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja, Semangat Kerja, Budaya Kerja Dan Keselamatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. Universitas Maritim Raja Ali Haji 2018.
- [33.] Dwilpalguna dan Mujiati. (2015). Pengaruh Penempatan, Motivasi Kerja, Dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja. *E-Jurnal Manajemen Unud*, Vol. 4, No. 9, 2015: 2777-2805 ISSN : 2302-8912.
- [34.] Billy Yanis Saputra, Susi Hendriani dan Machasin. 2017. Pengaruh Kompetensi Dan Penempatan Terhadap Semangat Kerja Dan Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Pendapatan Daerah Kabupaten Bengkalis. Vol. IX. No. 2 Mei 2017 *Jurnal Tepak Manajemen Bisnis*.
- [35.] Catur Nugroho, Jumiati Sasmita dan Yusni Maulida. 2019. Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasi, Semangat Kerja, Dan Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai PT. Sari Lembah Subur Kabupaten Pelalawan. Vol. XI. No. 3. Juli 2019 *Jurnal Tepak Manajemen Bisnis*.
- [36.] Yovita Aldilaningsari, Mochammad Al Musadieg dan Moch. Soe'oad Hakam 2014. Pengaruh Penempatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja (Studi pada Pegawai PT. Bank Jatim Cabang Malang)". *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB) | Vol. 9 No. 1 April 2014*.
- [37.] Almira Nanda Rizky Yani, Heru Susilo dan Ika Ruhana. 2016. Pengaruh Penempatan Pegawai Terhadap Motivasi Dan Kinerja (Studi pada pegawai PT Perkebunan Nusantara X (PG Watoetoelis) Sidoarjo) *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB) | Vol.30 No.1 Januari 2016*.
- [38.] Faris Afif, Connie Chairunnisa dan Pahman Habibi. 2020. Pengaruh Penempatan Kerja Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada CV. Gema Insani Press di Depok. *DIMENSI, VOL. 9, NO. 1 : 163- 177 MARET 2020 ISSN: 2085-9996*.
- [39.] Syalimono Siahaan dan Syaiful Bahri. 2019. Pengaruh Penempatan Pegawai, Motivasi, Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Maneggio: Jurnal Ilmiah Magister Manajemen*. Vol 2, No. 1, Maret 2019, 16-30. ISSN 2623-2634 (online).
- [40.] Husain, Bachtiar Arifudin. 2021. Pengaruh Penempatan dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Badan Amil Zakat Nasional BAZNAS (BAZIS) Provinsi DKI Jakarta. *Jurnal PERKUSI: Pemasaran, Keuangan, dan Sumber Daya Manusia VOLUME 1, NOMOR 4, OKTOBER 2021*.
- [41.] Syafitri, Marina. 2020. *The Effect Of Selection And Job Placement On Employee Performance In PT. Elastic White Elephant In Tangerang Regency*. Vol.1 No. 1 November 2020. Pege (Hal.) : 350 - 355 ISSN (online) : 2746 - 4482.
- [42.] Ni Wayan Anggreni, Ni Wayan Sitiari, Ni Luh Putu Indiani and Ni Putu Pertamawati. 2018. *The Effect of Leadership and Work Environment on Employee Performance Through Mediation of Work Spirit at Prama Sanur Beach Hotel*. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis Jagaditha Volume 5, Nomor 2, 2018*, pp. 84-91 EISSN 2579-8162 ISSN 2355-4150.

- [43.] Sari,Wisdalia Maya. 2018. Pengaruh Pelatihan dan Penempatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Journal of Economic, Business and Accounting (COSTING)* Volume 2 Nomor 1, Juli-Desember 2018 e-ISSN : 2597-5234.
- [44.] Azhari, IK Kusuma Wijaya.2021. Pengaruh Penempatan dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Disiplin Kerja Serta Dampaknya Pada Kinerja Pegawai Lembaga Layanan Pendidikan Tinggi (LLDIKTI) Wilayah VIII Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen dan Bisnis. Vol 6, No 1, Juni 2021. ISSN: 2528-1208 (print), ISSN: 2528-2077(online).
- [45.] Yosef Ferry Pratama dan, Dian Wismar' ein. 2018. Pengaruh Pelatihan dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Business Management Analysis Journal (BMAJ)* Vol. 1 No. 1 - Oktober 2018. ISSN 2623-0690 (Cetak).
- [46.] Lestari, B, Novitasari, D, Silitonga, N. dan Asbari, M. 2020. *The Effect of Recruitment and Career Development on The Spirit of Teachers' Work Performance in MTs Nurul Huda. Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Research*, 1(3), 108-121.
- [47.] Khamri, A. dan Heryanto,H.2019. *The Influence of the Work Environment, Work Discipline on the Spirit of Work and Its Impact on Employee Performance at the Dharmasraya District Health Office. Archives of Business Research*, 7(5), 205-216.
- [48.] Saifuddin, dan Kamaruddin. 2021. Pengaruh Rotasi Kerja, Motivasi Kerja dan Semangat Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Komisi Independen Pemilihan (KIP) Aceh. Vol. 2, No.4. September 2021. e-ISSN: 2721-382X.jurnal.uniki.ac.id/index.php/idm.
- [49.] Yeti Indrawati, Suratini, Achmad Idrus, Arry Pongtiku, Irwan A. Labo. 2021. Peran Semangat Kerja Untuk Mengatasi Gap Antara Penempatan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Perhubungan Provinsi Papua. Vol 4 No 1 (2021): ISSN : 2614-4190. *The Journal of Business and Management Research*, Januari 2021.
- [50.] Noedroho Boedijoewono, Pengantar Statistik Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Jilid 1 Edisi Keempat, UPP AMP YKPN, Yogyakarta,hal. 21
- [51.] Agus Irianto, 2004, Statistik Konsep Dasar dan Aplikasinya, Kencana, Jakarta, hal. 19.